

Kafalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

Izzatunnisa' Habiba Shalsabila, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to determine the mapping of research topics around the Kafalah contract in the Islamic Financial Inclusion using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Kafalah contract; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization regarding the Kafalah contract based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the Kafalah contract using a Library Research study. The results of the study show that: (1) based on the mapping of the distribution of journal publications, there are 32 journal publications regarding the Kafalah contract; (2) based on VOSviewer's bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results around the Kafalah contract are divided into 7 clusters and 87 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 3 main topics surrounding the Kafalah contract. The difference between this research and previous research is that this study explains and maps all research topics around the Kafalah contract so that future researchers can find the research gaps around the Kafalah contract. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around the Kafalah contract, which is often or rarely researched by researchers to be a reference for future researchers.

Keywords: Kafalah; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Inclusion

Introduction

As creatures created by Allah SWT, humans were created on earth as a Khalifah fil ard so that they could organize social life among each other. A well-organized life will also bring out goodness in the surroundings. We can see the good efforts that exist at this time from the progress of Conventional Banks towards Sharia Banks.

In the Sharia Banking Regulations, many products are used in its management and in the Sharia Finance Industry, one of the products used is the kafalah contract. The National Sharia Council and the Indonesian Ulema Council in 2000 issued a fatwa regarding the kafalah contract, namely through the National Sharia Council Fatwa Number 11/DSN-MUI/IV/2000. In a kafalah contract, a third party is the person who is the guarantor to pay the debt that has not been paid off by the person who has the obligation to pay it in advance.

Based on research via the official Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) there is a lot of research on kafalah contracts. There were 40 studies of kafalah contracts from 2011 to 2022. In some of the existing studies, researchers mostly discussed kafalah contracts in Sharia Banking. This Kafalah contract is also often compared with other sharia banking products such as wakalah contracts, hawalah contracts and other contracts.

This research is to map research topics around Kafalah cards in the Sharia Finance Industry in Indonesia by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics surrounding the Kafalah card, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research surrounding the Kafalah card. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics around the Kafalah card which are often or rarely studied by researchers, so that they can become references for future researchers.

Literature Review

Etymologically, kafalah means dhammu (combination), while in terms of terminology kafalah means combining the dependents of a kafil with the dependents of an ashil to fulfill demands on himself, or debts, or goods, or a job. Kafil is someone who has the obligation to fulfill the instructions of the makful bih (covered person). Ashil is someone whose debts will be borne.

Bibliometrics includes study methods that are descriptive in nature and are seen from authorship patterns which are used to determine the author's gender, type of work, level of collaboration, productivity of the industry where they work, and as the subject of the article. VOSviewer is a software application that can be used to describe bibliometrics, can provide references related to the research topics we need and much more (Effendy et al., 2021). The software used to map network data and visualization of map searches is VOSviewer. When using the software application, it can be directly downloaded and then converted into an EXE file and installed on various computer operating systems.

Library Research is a research method that has the aim of accumulating the essence of previous research and examining several expert views that have been written in the text.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is a Kafalah card. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Kafalah cards in the Sharia Finance Industry.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word "Kafalah" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around a Kafalah card using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on year of publication; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around a Kafalah card

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Based on the results of the analysis, this research is divided into 7 clusters with 87 topic. Following are the results of the analysis :

- Cluster 1 consisting of 16 topics, namely : regulations, agreement, benefits, BPJS employment, case, claim, company, contribution, fee, insurance, north Aceh regency, office, responsibility, risk, sawang district, term.
- Cluster 2 consists of 15 topics, namely: analysis, banda aceh, bsm, construction sector, counter guarantee, customer, data, descriptive analysis method, financing, implementation, interview, kafalah bil ujah contract, kafalah concept, kafalah financing, provisions.
- Cluster 3 consists of 15 topics, namely: collateral, coverage period, form, guaranteed party, kafalah contract, kafalah, khes, makful anhu, makful lahu, object, participant, pillar, question, tabarruaaa, value.
- Cluster 4 consists of 14 topics, namely: application, bank, bank guarantee, business, concept, contract, Indonesian Islamic bank, Islamic banking product, kafalah, practice, principle, product, service.
- Cluster 5 consists of 12 topics, namely: activity, fatwa, hawalah, Islamic finance company, kafalah agreement, position, principal, research, sharia, type, wakalah bil ujah.
- Cluster 6 consists of 8 topics, namely: bank btn syariah parepare, etc. mui iv, guarantee, guarantee service, guarantor, insurance, obligation, party.
- Cluster 7 consists of 7 topics, namely: debt, Hanafiyah school, library research, person, problem, property, study.

Mapping Research Topics Regarding the Implementation of the Kafalah Agreement in the Islamic Financial Inclusion using a Library Research Study

In this chapter, there are 8 research topics regarding the application of the Kafalah agreement to Sharia and Non-Sharia Financial Inclusion. All research uses a qualitative descriptive-analysis approach with library research and field research. Data collection techniques use documentation, observation and interviews with customers and company staff. As for the topics, namely:

1. Its application in take over financing. The research objects are: BMT UGT Sidogiri Capem Sukorejo, Blitar City and BMT UGT Sidogiri Capem Randuagung. The findings in this research are: first, the Kafalah bi Al-Ujah contract is easier and less complicated, second, its implementation is not in accordance with DSN-MUI provisions because the contract occurs without the knowledge of the makful lahu party; third, its implementation is not in accordance with sharia principles, because the nature of the ujah / wages in a tabarru' contract cannot be determined.
2. Its application in the insurance system in bancassurance guarantees. The findings in this research are: in practice, a sharia insurance company has not fulfilled the principles of Kafalah contracts according to sharia. This is because the coverage provided by sharia insurance companies does not meet the minimum deposit fee amount, which is 10%.
3. Its application in bank guarantee services. The first research finding is: there are benefits, both for Islamic banks and customers. The research object is: BTN Syariah Parepare. Islamic banks earn wages from issuing

guarantees, thereby increasing fee-based income. Meanwhile, customers get a guarantee without any collateral/ cash collateral with a large nominal amount, but only pay premiums, insurance, administration and stamp fees. In practice, Islamic banks apply the 5C principles (collateral, character, capacity, capital, condition of economy) in minimizing all financing risks. The second research findings, namely: research conducted at Bank Syariah Mandiri Banda Aceh. A bank guarantee is provided if the customer pays a maintenance guarantee of at least 10% of the value of the assets guaranteed. The third research findings, namely: research conducted at Bank Muamalat Indonesia KC Banda Aceh. The application of bank guarantees here is in accordance with sharia principles. The forms of collateral available include: tender, implementation, down payment and maintenance guarantees, with a deposit value of 100% cash collateral if the guarantee value is small, and 60% fixed asset plus 40% cash collateral if the guarantee value is greater than the value of the collateral asset. customers. The fourth research finding, namely: research conducted at Bank Syariah Mandiri KC Surabaya. Providing a bank guarantee is treated the same as providing credit financing to customers. So banks must apply 5C to determine the ability of debtor customers to pay off their debts. In providing this bank guarantee, the bank asks for collateral/collateral from the debtor customer, either in the form of a checking account or 45% of the project value.

4. Application in the Sharia Finance Industry. The research object is: As-Sakinah Kamal Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) has implemented the Kafalah contract in accordance with sharia principles and DSN-MUI provisions. Among the implementation procedures, namely: first, there is an administration fee for members when applying for Kafalah financing by submitting a stamped agreement letter; second, the contract will be executed if all three parties agree to the written terms; third, there is proper and neat accounting treatment of Kafalah contracts; fourth, there is the Kafalah reward; fifth, the contract is binding and cannot be canceled unilaterally.
5. Its application in sharia financing. The findings in this research are: its application in bank guarantees, Letters of Credit (L/C), corporate guarantees/personal guarantees. This financing is based on: first, Financial Services Authority Regulation no. 31/POJK.05/2014; second, Regulation of the Chairman of Bapepam and LK No. Per-03/BL/2007 and No. Per-04/BL/2007.
6. Application in insurance. The first research finding, namely: its application in the employment insurance agreement for Gampong Riseh Tunong, Sawang District, North Aceh Regency. Gampong officials use BPJS for socio-economic protection, namely the Work Accident Insurance (JKK) and Death Insurance (JKM) programs. The second research finding, namely: its application in Takaful Insurance. There are three conditions for granting takaful benefits, including: first, if the participant dies before the maturity period, then he becomes makful 'anhu, and the takaful funds can be used to pay his debts (Kafalah bi Al-Dain). Second, if the participant is still alive and the insurance period has ended, then he becomes kafil for other takaful participants, if another participant is struck by a disaster (Kafalah Al-Muallaqah). Third, if the participant resigns before the coverage period is over, then the Kafalah contract ends,

and he may do so at any time because the original law of the Kafalah contract is a tabarru' or voluntary contract, there are no attachments in it.

7. Its application in sharia cards. The findings in this research are: the application of sharia credit cards based on the Kafalah contract, which is of course different from conventional credit cards. This is based on fatwa no. 54/DSN-MUI/X/2006 concerning sharia cards. Sharia card dispute resolution can be done by: first, deliberation based on Bank Indonesia Regulation No. 7/46/PBI/2005 concerning contracts for the collection and distribution of funds for banks and Bank Indonesia Regulation no. 9/19/PBI/2007 concerning the implementation of sharia principles. Second, banking mediation is based on Bank Indonesia Regulation no. 8/5/PBI/2006 and No. 10/1/PBI/2008. Third, the National Sharia Arbitration Board (Basyarnas) based on Article 20 paragraph (2) No. 7/46/PBI/2005 and Article 4 paragraph (3) No. 9/19/PBI/2007. Fourth, Religious Courts are based on DSN-MUI.

Mapping Research Topics around Juridical Studies of Kafalah Contracts using Library Research Studies

In this chapter, there are 4 research topics regarding the juridical study of Kafalah contracts on Sharia and Non-Sharia Financial Inclusion. All research uses a qualitative descriptive-analysis approach with library research and field research. Data collection techniques use documentation, observation and interviews with customers and company staff. As for the topics, namely:

1. The Kafalah contract is based on the Koran, Hadith and Ijmak. The findings in this research are: first, Surah Yusuf verses 66 and 72; second, hadith narrated by Al-Nasa'iy from Abdullah bin Abu Qatadah, hadith number 4613; third, Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) Chapter XII Articles 335-361 concerning the Kafalah contract; fourth, hadith narrated by Al-Bukhariy from Salamah bin Akwa, hadith number 2295; fifth, hadith narrated by Ibn Majah from Uthman bin Abdullah bin Mauhab, hadith number 2407; sixth, hadith narrated by Ahmad from Salamah, hadith number 15913.
2. The Kafalah contract is based on muamalah fiqh. The findings in this research are: the meaning, the pillars (kafil /person who guarantees, makful 'anhu/madin/ashil/ person who owes money, makful bihi/object/debt, makful lahu/da'in/ person who owes money and shighat / ijab qabul), the distribution is based on the object/ mahal (Kafalah with life and property), the distribution is based on its nature (Kafalah Muthlaqah and Muqayyadah), the form of the contract is based on its implementation (munjaz/tanjiz, mulak/ta'lik, sukakad/taukid), the terms of the object, implementation of the contract, wisdom of the contract, benefits of the contract and the end of the Kafalah contract.
3. The Kafalah contract is based on the DSN-MUI fatwa. The findings in this research are: first, fatwa no. 11/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 concerning Kafalah. If we look at the opinions of the four schools of thought, wages are not permitted in the Kafalah contract, because the original law of the Kafalah contract is the tabarru' contract. The reason DSN-MUI allows wages in Kafalah contracts is based on the opinion of contemporary ulama who follow changes in time and place. Therefore, there are Muslim scholars who say that whoever tries to bring benefits to others, then he has the right to receive a reward, whether this is required at the start or not.

Second, fatwa no. 74/DSN-MUI/I/2009 concerning sharia guarantees. In the fatwa there is a discussion of compensation for Kafalah services, ta'widh and fines for late payment. Third, fatwa no. 57/DSN-MUI/V/2007 concerning Letter of Credit (L/C) with a Kafalah bil Al-Ujrah agreement.

Mapping Research Topics around Other Issues Related to the Kafalah Contract using a Library Research Study

In this chapter, there are 6 research topics surrounding other issues related to the Kafalah contract on Sharia and Non-Sharia Financial Inclusion. All research uses a qualitative descriptive-analysis approach with library research and field research. Data collection techniques use documentation, observation and interviews with customers and company staff. As for the topics, namely:

1. Rates of compensation for services/wages/ ujarah in the Kafalah contract. The first research finding is: there is a legal transformation of the origin of the Kafalah contract, which was originally a tabarru' contract and changed to a mu'awadhat contract, which is a product of the Kafalah bi Al-Ujrah contract. This transformation is in accordance with the DSN-MUI fatwa while still being based on benefits and sharia economic principles. The second research finding, namely: a model for calculating benefits for retired and pre-retired kafalah services at PT Jamkrindo Syariah Syariah Division using a website- based application with the prototype method. This application is based on user experience and is expected to run effectively so that it can provide fast and accurate fee calculation results to sales marketing even when they are outside the office. This innovation can make the company more competitive with other competitors.
2. Kafalah guarantee for debts for people who die without assets. The findings in this research are: the process of paying the debts of a person who dies without assets. Someone owes a debt because of good intentions, but he is unable to pay it, so his heirs bear the debt. If the heirs are also unable to pay it or are unwilling to pay it, then Kafalah bi Al-Dain is applied, or becomes the responsibility of another person who is deemed capable of paying it.
3. The Kafalah contract is based on philosophy. The findings in this research are: this transaction is based on benefit, including masalahah murlahah, mu'tabarrah and mulghah. The basic principles in economic law include the principles of monotheism, justice and amar ma'ruf nahi munkar. In carrying out the Kafalah contract, it is necessary to pay attention to the maqashid sharia khamsah, namely: hifdz al-din/ protecting religion, hifdz al-nafs /protecting the soul, hifdz al-nasl /protecting offspring, hifdz al-'aql /protecting reason and hifdz al-mal /guarding property.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding Kafalah contracts in the Sharia Finance Industry during the period 2013 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there were 52 published journal articles. Second, based on Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer bibliometric studies, the results of network visualization around

Kafalah contracts in the Sharia Finance Industry are divided into 7 clusters and 87 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 16 topics, cluster 2 consists of 15 topics, cluster 3 consists of 15 topics, cluster 4 consists of 14 topics, cluster 5 consists of 12 topics, cluster 6 consists of 8 topics, and cluster 7 consists of 7 topics. Third, based on Mapping Research Topics using Library Research studies, there are 3 topics related to Kafalah contracts in the Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Application; (2) Juridical Study; and (3) Other Issues Relating to the Kafalah Agreement in the Islamic Financial Inclusion.

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